

SINGLE DIODE MODEL APPLIED TO PV MODULE AGING

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ABSTRACT: The outdoor exposure of PV modules to different climatic variables and physical stresses reduces the power delivery capacity of a PV modules over time. The degradation of the PV performance over lifetime is usually determined within the variation of Power at maximum power point (P_{MPP}) and Fill Factor (FF) where the same magnitude of losses of the P_{MPP} can have different causes with different evolution over time. The physic based understanding and modeling of the performance, using the IV curve measurements, can be used to estimate important device parameters and evaluate the health state of the system. In this context the physical model of PV could provide more granulated information about degradation and underlying mechanisms to make batter predictions about service life. Single diode model parameter evolution was estimated from 8 years of outdoor IV curves measurements under a range of operating conditions without translating to STC. The results show that the main ageing factors are closely related to the decrease in short-circuit current due to the optical degradation and increase in series resistance regardless of outdoor operating conditions.

Keywords: Degradation, Single Diode Model, CMA-ES, parameter estimation

1 INTRODUCTION

To estimate the profitability of the photovoltaic investment it is essential to accurately quantify and define all the relevant risk factors of long term performance losses. The photovoltaic performance output is known to decline over time and to quantify it, the degradation rate is commonly used.

The PV operating lifetime is mainly determined by the stability and resistance of PV modules to different internal and mechanical loads. These loads are closely related to differences in meteorological exposure depending on the location of the installation and are affecting various module technologies differently. Depending on the technology and its geographical location the degradation rates will be different, specific climatic conditions provoke certain degradation modes more severe. Exemplarily, modules deployed in hot and humid climates were reported with a considerably wider variety of degradation modes. [1]

There are several degradation rate calculation methodologies which are based on various statistical approaches [1] but they fail to provide any information on the mechanisms behind degradation. The degradation of the PV module is closely related to the variation of the internal parameters of the solar cell, namely the short circuit current, ideality factor, saturation current and series and shunt resistances. Observing their evolution in a range of different operating conditions could provide clues about degradation mechanisms.

The commonly observed degradation mechanism include material corrosion, delamination, discoloration of encapsulant over cells, and breakage or cracks of modules. These degradation modes affect the PV characteristics in three ways: decreasing transmittance τ , increasing series resistance R_s , and decreasing shunt resistance R_{sh} [2]. There are several factors such as corrosion of glass, discoloration of encapsulant and degradation of anti-reflecting coating which can cause optical degradation.

The series and shunt resistance evolution represents the summation of several loss mechanisms in a solar cell. Losses due to resistance introduced in cell solder bonds, emitter and base regions, cell metallization and cell-interconnect bus bars all contribute to the value of R_s [3].

Shunt resistance can arise from imperfections on the device surface as well as from leakage currents across the edge of the cell [4]. The R_{sh} value represents any parallel high-conductivity paths across the solar cell p-n junction where an increase in R_s results in a drop in voltage output while a decrease in R_{sh} will reduce current output [5]. Work by Dyk and Meyer demonstrated that by increasing R_s from 0.36 to 1.8 Ω both the P_{MPP} and FF were reduced by 25%, making it clear that the performance is strongly influenced by loss resistance values. Therefore, both R_s and R_{sh} needs to be recognized and their evolution understood in order to improve the module service life forecast. According to the International Energy Agency Photovoltaic Power System Program report: Review of Failures of Photovoltaic Modules [6] if the shunt resistance decreases due to shunt paths in the PV cell and/or interconnections, the I-V curve near ISC becomes sloped. A lower slope of the I-V curve near V_{oc} indicates an increase of the series resistance in the PV module. The series resistance in the module could increase due to an increase in interconnection resistance, corrosion in junction box or interconnects and slacks joints.

The focus of the approach is to track the evolution of IV curves and SDM parameters over time in stable irradiation and temperature conditions to gain insights into the degradation of PV devices. The evolution of single diode parameters, namely the series resistance (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) could at least partially reveal the fundamental mechanisms of degradation and their influence on the open circuit voltage V_{oc} , short circuit I_{sc} and PMPP. Therefore, both R_s and R_{sh} need to be recognized and we need to understand their evolution with changing irradiance (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** (b)) and temperature conditions in order to improve the module performance forecast.

2 METHOD

To evaluate the parameter values in different operating conditions the narrow window method is used (figure 1) where parameters are extracted at certain outdoor temperature and irradiance conditions, initially chosen from standard IEC 61853-1. Without translating to STC conditions the uncertainty of the measurements is reduced. We defined narrow windows with a range of $G \pm 2W/m^2$

and $T \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The size of this window is a compromise between sufficient number of data points and acceptable spread between IV curves measured within the same year. Data from high irradiance conditions are used since they show less spread. The single diode model (SDM) is used for comparing the evolution of parameters. It is confirmed that this model provides an accurate prediction of outdoor measurements [10], at the same time allows a good compromise between accuracy and simplicity while avoiding the additional complexity of the double diode model.

Figure 1: Data points where IV curves are available shown over the Irradiance and temperature domain. The initial reference points are shown in red.

Figure 2: Example of selected IV curves at $1000 \pm 2\text{W/m}^2$ Irradiance and $T = 50 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

The single diode model (SDM) is used for comparing the evolution of parameters.

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(\exp\left(\frac{V+R_s I}{nV_t}\right) - 1 \right) - \frac{V+R_s I}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

I_L = Photo-generated current (A)

I_0 = Dark saturation current (A)

n = Diode ideality factor (unit less)

$V_{th} = \frac{N_s k T_c}{q}$ Thermal voltage (V) for the module, which is determined from cell temperature T_c (K) Boltzmann constant k ($\frac{J}{K}$) and the elementary charge q (coloumb)

k = Boltzmann constant (1.38066×10^{-23} J/K)

q = Elementary charge (1.60218×10^{-19} Coloumb)

R_s = Series resistance (Ω)

R_{sh} = Shunt resistance (Ω)

The values of R_s are considered for the module level. Parameter estimation for a single diode model is challenging and non-trivial due to the implicit equation describing the relationship between current and voltage. Equation 1 cannot be solved for current (or voltage)

explicitly using elementary functions. It can be expressed as a function of voltage $I = I(V)$ (or $V = V(I)$) by using the transcendental Lambert's W function [7] as used in [8]. Lambert's W function is the solution $W(x)$ of the equation $x = W(x) \exp[W(x)]$ using this function we can write $I = I(V)$ as shown in equation 2.

$$I = \frac{R_{sh}}{R_{sh}+R_s} (I_L + I_0) - \frac{V}{R_{sh}+R_s} - \frac{nV_{th}}{R_s} W \left(\frac{R_s I_0}{nV_{th}} \frac{R_{sh}}{R_{sh}R_s} \exp\left(\frac{R_{sh}}{R_{sh}+R_s} \frac{R_s (I_L + I_0) + V}{nV_{th}}\right) \right) \quad (2)$$

The values of the parameter extracted by optimization techniques depend on the objective function used in the algorithm. In this study the root mean squared error (RMSE) was used and the difference between measured current and the one obtained using the estimated parameters was calculated as shown in equation 3. Here, N is the number of samples, $i_{estimated}$ and $i_{measured}$ are the estimated and measured values for current respectively, the set of parameters, which produce the smallest RMSE are used as extracted. The ideal value of the objective function should be 0, however because of the electrical noise and measurement errors it should be minimized as much as possible.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (i_{estimated} - i_{measured})^2} \quad (3)$$

For the nonlinear optimization problem the Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy was used (CMA-ES) [9]. CMA-ES is a stochastic numerical optimization algorithm for difficult (non-convex) optimization problems in continuous search spaces. Root finding and optimization methods require initial estimates of parameter values, selection of an error metrics and setting of conditions to determine convergence. Different choices for these aspects may results in different parameter values being obtained from the same data. The initial parameters were estimated from the first IV-curve measurement at 4 different operating conditions and were not changed after 8 years. The absolute error between iteration that is acceptable for convergence was set on $1.e-5$ and the optimization procedures converged for every IV curve parameter estimation in around 400 iterations with the RMSE between 0.005-0.008.

The parameter estimation for a single I-V curve takes approximately 3 minutes calculation time on i5 8GB RAM PC.

3 DATA USED

From EDF monitoring test site located in CSA dry-summer or Mediterranean climate (according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification) large quantities of data were collected in 1 minute interval. 8 years of IV curves measurements from Poly Si 72 cell module were used to estimate the difference in parameter values at the first year of the installation and in one year after 8 years of outdoor operation. Maximum power point and the fill factor were extrapolated from the I-V curves.

Weather data includes irradiance, ambient temperature and module temperature. Missing values, outliers representing measurement or sensor error were omitted from analysis.

4 RESULTS

IV curves characteristics and SDM parameters (R_S, R_{SH}, I_{ph}) were estimated in 4 different narrow windows namely: 1000W/m²-50°C, 1000W/m²-45°C, 950W/m²-45°C and 900W/m²-40°C. High irradiation conditions were chosen because the IV curves variation is reduced. Additional filtering of 2 standard deviation range around the mean values was used to additionally control the spread of measured and estimated values.

Fig 3: Percentage change of performance indicators after 8 years of outdoor installation, at 4 different G, T conditions

Percentage change of IV mean values before and after 8 years of outdoor operation in different conditions (fig 3) shows that the largest decrease regardless of the operating conditions (figure 3) is in Pmpp, followed by the Isc, 5.8% and 4.7% respectively. The percentage change in Voc is approximately 0.5% where the change in FF is around 0.3%.

The change in photocurrent averaged over all operating conditions (figure 4) is -4.7% where the values of photocurrent don't show any temperature dependencies.

Figure 4: Difference in photocurrent after 8 years of outdoor exposure in 4 different irradiance and temperature combination

The dependence of photocurrent I_{ph} on incident solar irradiation G and cell temperature T is expressed as:

$$I = I_{ph} = [I_{pv,ref} + k_1(T - T_{ref})] \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \tau \quad (4)$$

Where $I_{pv,ref}$ is photocurrent at the reference conditions, usually the standard test conditions (STC) of irradiance 1000 W/m², cell temperature 25°C, and air mass 1.5; k_1 (A/K) is the temperature coefficient of short-circuit current, T and T_{ref} are the actual and reference cell temperature, G and G_{ref} are the actual irradiation and reference irradiation, the dimensionless variable τ measures the transmittance of PV module, which decreases over time due to the optical degradation. The initial value of transmittance is 1 [12].

τ	Isc (A)	Voc (V)	PMPP	FF
1	8.3	33.44	198	0.69
0.75	6.2	33.2	156	0.68
0.5	4.3	32.8	112	0.69

Table 1: Effect of decreasing transmittance on PV characteristic parameters.

In table 1 it is shown how the decreasing transmittance τ reduces both Isc and Voc. When the transmittance is reduced for 25% both the Isc and Pmpp are reduced approximately for the same percentage where FF and Voc show slight variation.

Comparing the series resistance in different narrow windows (figure 5) don't show any changes in the slope. Averaging over all operating conditions the change in R_s is 9.4% after 8 years.

Figure 5: Difference in series resistance after 8 years of outdoor exposure in 4 different irradiance and temperature combinations

The values of shunt resistance don't show considerable degradation in 8 years of outdoor operation. At the same time the values of shunt resistance is difficult to estimate from IV-curves and SDM.

In order to improve the module performance forecast and service life prediction the temporal evolution of the parameters and their dependency on changing irradiance and temperature conditions needs to be understood.

Figure 6: Series resistance temperature dependence at 1000W/m² and temperature range from 20-60°C at the beginning (blue) and after 8 years of outdoor exposure (orange).

Comparing the series resistance temperature dependence show no changes in the slope in time (table 2). Values of R^2, α, β show no considerable change in time.

	First Year	Last Year
R^2	0.942	0.874
α	0.356	0.344
β	0.0013	0.0025

Table 2: coefficients of the linear models of series resistance temperature dependence in first year of operation and after 8 years.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study an outdoor IV curves parameter estimation methodology was applied to study the degradation process of PV. The method relies on single diode circuit based model of PV electrical characteristics. The approach is based on a narrow window method of different environmental condition (irradiation and temperature) combinations and allows to analyze the outdoor data without conversion to STC.

The results show that the main aging factor of fielded PV module is the decrease of short-circuit current where the main power loss is mostly caused by the optical degradation of the PV modules followed by the increase of series resistance. Possible degradation modes affecting the analyzed module are yellowing and browning of EVA, delamination and appearance of bubbles or anti-reflecting coating degradation. Increase in series resistance suggest that there is a possible corrosion on metal bars or interconnectors in PV module.

Here, the transmittance $\tau(t)$, R_{sh} and the series resistance $R_s(t)$ are time dependent variables presenting the aging process of materials over time, thereby the I-V characteristics are not only a function of irradiation G and cell temperature T , but also a function of time t .

The results of the study should be confirmed with the visual inspection of the fielded module and electrical characterization in the laboratory. The ageing patterns are highly dependent on PV technology and climate that the modules are exposed to. Results should be compared with the IV curves gathered from different climatic conditions or/and different technologies to be able to make specific climate and technology related service life predictions.

More than 8 years of IV curves measurements in outdoor should be used to detect degradation modes that are appearing after that period. The shunt resistance values are not showing any degradation in 8 years of outdoor operation.

One of the weaknesses of using a single diode model is not considering the possible mismatch among the cell of photovoltaic module. It is known that the cells in the PV modules don't degrade with the same rate where the cells closer to the edge of the module degrade faster.

To improve the yield and service life prediction forecasts of the PV plants it is essential to include the degradation and related degradation modes based on parameter evolution which should be technology and climate dependent.

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